

BINDERS SYNDROME AND ANAESTHESIA

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ABSTRACT Binders syndrome is an uncommon congenital facial deformity. 'It is a rare form of maxillofacial dysplasia with several nasal and mid-face deformities. There has been sparse literature about anaesthetic concerns regarding this uncommon disorder. Binder's syndrome is associated with difficult airway and difficulty in nasal intubation. Difficult airway cart must be kept ready, both during intubation and extubation. Also, it is associated with mental retardation, cervical spine abnormalities and dental problems. As perioperative physicians, we must be aware of this anomaly and its peri-operative implications. We describe the anaesthetic considerations in the case of Binder's syndrome in a young female patient presenting for nasal reconstruction. To the best of our knowledge, there has been no previous reported article on anaesthetic implications of Binders syndrome.

KEYWORDS Binders Syndrome; Difficult Airway; Nasal intubation; Maxillofacial dysplasia; Congenital anomaly; Reconstructive surgery; Anaesthetic concerns.

INTRODUCTION

Binder's syndrome is a rare, congenital, facio-maxillary deformity requiring staged plastic and reconstructive surgery. Since it is an uncommon condition, peri-operative physicians may be unaware of its anaesthetic considerations. Apart from the possibility of the difficult airway, there can be other co-existing conditions like mental retardation, cervical spine abnormalities and dental problems. Difficult airway cart, including fibre-optic bronchoscope, must be kept ready both during intubation and extubation. This article describes the anaesthetic management of a case of Binder's syndrome posted for elective nasal reconstruction. Even though the problems associated with Binders syndrome were not encountered in our case, the anesthesiologist must be aware of this rare syndromic disorder for adequate preparation to ensure a successful perioperative outcome.

CASE REPORT

A 19-year-old female patient presented for elective nasal deformity correction. She was a known case of Binders syndrome. On pre-anaesthetic evaluation, all routine investigations were within normal limits. She had complaints of occasional nasal obstruction and nasal twang in speech. There was no recent history of upper respiratory infection. On airway examination, Mallampatti grade was class 2. Other remarkable facial features included a depressed nasal bridge, prominent upper lips, slight mandibular prognathism and flattened malar prominences. Neck movements and airway distances were within normal limits. The systemic organ system evaluation was also normal. The surgeons wanted an oral airway which did not come in their way of nasal manipulation. Standard general anaesthesia was instituted after preoxygenation with all precautions of a difficult airway. On direct laryngoscopy, the modified Cormack and Lehane grading was 2. An oral flexometallic cuffed endotracheal (size 6.5mm) was inserted and fixed at the centre of the lower lip. After confirming bilateral air entry, oral packing was done, with care taken to count the oral pack in the surgical swab and marking it on the exterior as well. All standard ASA monitors were instituted. The surgery lasted around two hours and was uneventful. Patient was extubated, after removal of oral packing according to standard protocol, with stable vital parameters throughout the perioperative period. Difficult airway cart was kept handy at the time of extubation also. The patient was observed in the postanesthesia care unit for six hours, before

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being shifted to the ward in a stable condition.

DISCUSSION

Binder's syndrome [1] is an uncommon congenital condition with characteristic facial features. It was identified and defined by Von Binder in 1962 [2], though described earlier by Noyes in 1939. It is also called "maxilla-nasal dysostosis", with the following six characteristic features [3]: arhinoid face, intermaxillary hypoplasia (associated with malocclusion), abnormal position of the nasal bones, nasal mucosal atrophy, anterior nasal spine agenesis and a lack of frontal sinuses. There is a failure of development in the premaxillary area with associated deformities of the nasal skeleton and the overlying soft tissues (rhino-cephalic dysplasia) [4]. Patients have an unusually flat, underdeveloped midface and an abnormally short nose with the flat nasal bridge, lack of nasal tip projection, peri-alar flattening, mandibular prognathism and an acute nasolabial angle. Other associated features include mental retardation, bilateral hearing loss, prenatal vitamin K deficiency, irregularities in the cervical spine[5] (e.g. Separate odontoid process, short posterior arch, and spina bifida occulta), prominent lips, poor oro-dental hygiene and psychological problems due to cosmetic defect. According to Holmstrom, inheritance of this syndrome may be an autosomal recessive trait with incomplete penetrance [6]. These patients present for surgical correction of facial deformities and orthodontic treatment of dental problems. The main surgery performed is a nasal reconstruction with bone or cartilage grafts[7]. Others include maxillary protraction with rapid palatal expansion. Patients can present for repeated surgeries due to graft resorption or an unsatisfactory appearance. The main anaesthetic consideration is the presence of difficult airway. Nasal intubation should not be attempted in these patients due to reduced nasal passages and possibility of trauma during tube passage. Insertion of a nasogastric tube can also be challenging. Direct laryngoscopy must be gentle and cautious due to dental malocclusion and crowding. Complete difficult airway cart[8] must be prepared and checked preoperatively. Associated abnormalities with Binder's syndrome also need to be evaluated in the pre-anesthetic assessment. An otorhinolaryngologist evaluation, cervical spine X-rays, psychological counselling, dental opinion and measures to improve oral hygiene are vital in the preoperative period. Awake fiberoptic oral intubation (after adequate pre-oxygenation) can be attempted under intravenous sedation with Dexmedetomidine or Remifentanyl infusion, along with upper airway blocks, nebulised lignocaine and "say go" technique during fiberoptic bronchoscopy. If airway assessment is otherwise normal, a video-laryngoscopic guided oral intubation can be done after intravenous and/or inhalational induction, with the muscle relaxant given after confirming correct tube position. A wire-reinforced tracheal tube is preferable to prevent its kinking during head and neck movements during surgery. Endotracheal tube fixation requires special attention as it should not come in the way of the surgical field and at the same time do not cause a drag on the angles of the mouth. Secure tube fixation at the centre of the lower lip may be preferred to help the surgeon assess the symmetry of the mid-face during reconstruction. Oral packing may be done to prevent blood and secretions trickling into the lower airway during surgery. Care must be taken in documenting the use of oro-pharyngeal packs (with a radio-opaque line) and remembering to remove them at the end of surgery[9]. Since osteotomy and grafts are required for the surgery, pain management (multi-modal techniques) must be given adequate

importance. Temperature maintenance (normothermia) must be ensured, especially in prolonged procedures with the help of patient and fluid warmers. Difficult airway precautions must be followed at the time of extubation as well, including tube exchanger device. There has been no anesthesia-related literature concerning Binder's syndrome. Most importantly, the attending anesthesiologist must be aware of this rare syndrome and its associated anomalies for improving the overall perioperative outcome of the affected patients. This case was reported to improve the knowledge bank of the anesthesiologists worldwide, to handle such cases effectively.

CONCLUSION

Binder's syndrome, though rare, must be kept in mind while anaesthetizing a patient for facio-maxillary reconstructive surgery. A thorough pre-operative evaluation for concurrent conditions and complete airway assessment is of paramount importance. Since these patients can present for several staged procedures, multiple anaesthetic exposures is a possibility, especially in a scenario of the difficult airway. Awareness of this rare syndromic disorder enables the anesthesiologist to prepare the operation theatre adequately and to manage the associated problems successfully.

COMPETING INTERESTS

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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